

Studies on Chromones and Flavones. Part VIII:* Studies on 4'-Hydroxyflavone

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3'-Acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone prepared from 4'-hydroxyflavone has been condensed with benzaldehyde and anisaldehyde and the 3'-cinnamoyl derivatives obtained have been converted into 2-(6'-flavonyl)- and 2-(4''-methoxy-6'-flavonyl) chromone respectively by heating with selenium dioxide. The former chromone has also been synthesised by Baker-Venkataraman transformation of 3'-acetyl-4'-benzoyloxyflavone and subsequent cyclization of the β -diketone obtained. 3'-Acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation gave 2'-methyl-3'-acetyl-2,6'-bichromonyl.

3'-Formyl- and 3'-acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone have been condensed with ethyl bromoacetate and the esters obtained hydrolysed to the corresponding acids which on heating with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride gave 2-(5'-benzofuranyl)- and 2-(3'-methyl-5'-benzofuranyl) chromone respectively.

ALTHOUGH a number of substitution reactions have been carried out and heterocyclic rings built on the benzo- γ -pyrone unit of various flavones the studies on substitution in the side phenyl nucleus and building up of other heterocyclic rings on the side phenyl nucleus have been meagre. The present work deals with such synthesis from 4'-hydroxyflavones^{1,2}.

4'-Acetoxyflavone² on Fries migration with aluminium chloride at 140° gave a product which gave a deep violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and hence it has been assigned the 3'-acetyl-4'-hydroxy flavone structure. The same compound was also obtained from 4'-hydroxyflavone by Friedel-Crafts acetylation with acetic anhydride and aluminium chloride at 140°-50°.

On condensation with benzaldehyde in presence of alkali it gave 3'-cinnamoyl-4'-hydroxyflavone, which on cyclodehydrogenation with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol gave 2-(6'-flavonyl) chromone (Ia). The same product was obtained by the Baker-Venkataraman transformation of 3'-acetyl-4'-benzoyloxyflavone in the presence of pyridine and potassium hydroxide at room temperature and subsequent cyclisation of the β -diketone obtained with conc. sulphuric acid.

3'-Acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone was also condensed with anisaldehyde in the presence of alkali when 3'-(*p*-methoxy cinnamoyl)-4'-hydroxyflavone was obtained. This on cyclodehydrogenation with selenium dioxide in isoamyl alcohol gave 2-(4''-methoxy-6'-flavonyl)chromone (Ib).

3'-Acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone was condensed with ethyl bromoacetate to get 3'-acetyl-4'-carbethoxy-methoxyflavone which was then hydrolysed to the corresponding acid with conc. sulphuric acid. On

heating the acid with freshly fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride it furnished 2-(3'-methyl-5'-benzofuranyl)chromone (IIa).

3'-Formyl-4'-hydroxyflavone was obtained by refluxing 4'-hydroxyflavone with excess of hexamine in acetic acid. It gave a deep violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. On Perkin acetylation it gave 2(6'-coumarinyl)chromone (III).

3'-Formyl-4'-hydroxyflavone on condensation with ethyl bromoacetate gave 3'-formyl-4'-carbethoxy-methoxyflavone. This was hydrolysed to the corresponding acid with conc. sulphuric acid. The acid was cyclised by heating it with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride to 2(5'-benzofuranyl) chromone (IIb).

Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation of 4'-hydroxy-3'-acetylflavone with freshly fused sodium acetate and acetic anhydride at 170°-80° yielded a product which was not soluble in sodium hydroxide solution and did not give a colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. It analysed for 2'-methyl-3'-acetyl-2,6'-bichromonyl (IV).

It has thus been possible to synthesise a variety of chromone derivatives with different oxygen heterocyclic substituents in the 2-position

Experimental

3'-Acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone : 4'-Acetoxyflavone² (1 g.) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (2 g.) and heated in an oil bath at 140° for 2 hr., ice cold hydrochloric acid was then added and the product obtained crystallised from acetic acid. M.P. 253°. Yield 0.6 g. It gave violet colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride. (Found : C, 73.13; H, 4.58; C₁₇H₁₂O₄ requires C, 72.85; H, 4.32%).

4'-Hydroxyflavone (1 mole; 2.2 g.) was mixed with anhydrous aluminium chloride (4.4 mole; 5.7 g.) and acetic anhydride (1.1 mole; 1.5 ml.) and heated at 140°–50° in an oil bath for 1.5 hr. The product obtained on working up as usual crystallised from acetic acid. M.P. and mixed m.p. with 3'-acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone described above was 253°. Yield 1.8 g.

The 2,4-D.N.P. of the above acetyl flavone was prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene. M.P. 315° (decomp.) (Found : N, 12.73. $C_{21}H_{16}O_7N_4$ requires N, 12.84%).

3'-Cinnamoyl-4'-hydroxyflavone : To a mixture of 3'-acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone (1 g.) and benzaldehyde (1 ml.) in alcohol (25 ml.) potassium hydroxide (5 g. in 5 ml. water) was added and the mixture kept overnight. The mixture after dilution with water and acidification gave a product which crystallised from benzene in dark yellow woolly needles (0.5 g.), m.p. 187°.

It gave a wine red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and dark red colouration with conc. sulphuric acid. It also gave a positive Wilson test³. (Found : C, 77.94; H, 4.20. $C_{24}H_{16}O_4$ requires C, 78.26; H, 4.30%).

The methyl ether : The above ketone (1 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (50 ml.) with dimethyl sulphate (2 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) for 10 hr. on a steam bath. The product obtained on removal of acetone and addition of water crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether. M.P. 153°. (Found : C, 78.16; H, 4.66. $C_{25}H_{18}O_4$ requires C, 78.52; H, 4.71%).

2-(6'-Flavonyl)chromone : The above hydroxy ketone (1 g.) was dissolved in dry isoamyl alcohol (15 ml.) and the solution refluxed with selenium dioxide (3 g.) in an oil bath at 140°–50° for 18 hr. It was filtered hot. On cooling, the flavone was obtained. It crystallised from benzene in white small needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 265°. (Found : C, 78.59; H, 3.51. $C_{24}H_{14}O_4$ requires C, 78.68; H, 3.82%).

3'-Acetyl-4'-benzoyloxyflavone : A mixture of 3'-acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone (5 g.), benzoyl chloride (4 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (10 g.) in acetone (50 ml.) was refluxed on a steam bath for

12 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water crystallised from acetic acid. M.P. 190°. Yield 4 g. (Found : C, 74.81; H, 4.23. $C_{24}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 75.01; H, 4.17%).

3'-(ω -benzoylacetyl) 4'-hydroxyflavone : The above benzoyl derivative (1 g.) was dissolved in pyridine (20 ml.) and powdered potassium hydroxide (4 g.) was added with stirring. The reaction mixture after keeping for 4 hr. at room temperature was poured in ice cold hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was crystallised from dilute acetic acid. M.P. 247°–48°. It was soluble in alkali and gave brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. (Found : C, 74.94; H, 4.07. $C_{24}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 75.01; H, 4.17%).

Cyclisation : The above β -diketone (1 g.) was mixed with conc. sulphuric acid (5 ml.) and kept at room temperature for 4 hr. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in ice cold water crystallised from benzene. M.P. and mixed m.p. with 2(6'-flavonyl) chromone described above was 265°.

3'-(*p*-methoxy cinnamoyl) 4'-hydroxyflavone : A mixture of 3'-acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone (1 g.) and anisaldehyde (1 ml.) in alcohol (25 ml.) was kept overnight with potassium hydroxide (5 g. in 5 ml. water). It was then diluted with water and acidified with conc. hydrochloric acid. The product obtained crystallised from benzene in orange yellow needles (1.5 g.), m.p. 179°–80°. It gave wine red colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride and dark orange colouration with conc. sulphuric acid. It also gave a positive Wilson test³. (Found : C, 75.34; H, 4.44. $C_{25}H_{18}O_5$ requires C, 75.38; H, 4.52%).

The methyl ether : The above ketone (1 g.) was refluxed in dry acetone (50 ml.) with dimethyl sulphate (2 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (4 g.) for 10 hr. on a steam bath. The product obtained on removal of acetone and addition of water crystallised from dilute acetic acid in pale yellow needles, m.p. 185°. (Found : C, 75.26; H, 4.61. $C_{26}H_{20}O_5$ requires C, 75.72; H, 4.85%).

2-(4''-Methoxy-6'-flavonyl) chromone : The above hydroxy ketone (1 g.) was refluxed with selenium dioxide (3 g.) in isoamyl alcohol (15 ml.) in an oil

bath at 140°–50° for 18 hr. It was filtered hot and the flavone obtained on cooling the filtrate was crystallised from xylene in pale yellow shining needles, m.p. 270°. (Found : C, 75.56; H, 3.89. $C_{25}H_{16}O_5$ requires C, 75.75; H, 4.04%).

3'-Acetyl-4'-carbethoxymethoxyflavone : 3'-Acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone (1.5 g) was refluxed with ethyl bromo acetate (1 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) in dry acetone for 6 hr. on a water bath. The acetone was removed and the reaction mixture was added to water. The ester which separated was crystallised from benzene. M.P. 175°–77°. Yield 1.1 g. (Found : C, 68.47; H, 4.80. $C_{21}H_{18}O_6$ requires, C, 68.85; H, 4.92%)

3'-Acetyl-4'-carboxymethoxyflavone : The above ester (1 g.) was kept with con. sulphuric acid for 4 hr. at room temperature. The product obtained on pouring the reaction mixture in water was extracted with sodium bicarbonate solution. The product obtained on acidification with con. hydrochloric acid crystallised from acetic acid in needles (0.8 g.), m.p. 258° (effev). (Found : C, 67.94; H, 4.26. $C_{19}H_{14}O_6$ requires C, 67.45; H, 4.14%).

2(3'-Methyl-5'-benzofuranyl) chromone : The above acid (1 g.) was refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 ml.) on a wire gauze for 2½ hr. The reaction mixture was poured in water and kept overnight. The solid obtained was crystallised from dilute acetic acid. M.P. 175°. Yield 0.4 g. (Found : C, 79.20; H, 3.98. $C_{19}H_{12}O_3$ requires C, 79.17; H, 4.16%).

3'-Formyl-4'-hydroxyflavone : 4'-Hydroxyflavone (1 g.) was dissolved in glacial acetic acid (30 ml.) and refluxed gently with hexamethylene tetramine (4 g.) till the colour of the reaction mixture changed to dark brown (about 1 hr.). Hydrochloric acid (15 ml., 1 : 1) was added to the reaction mixture and the heating continued for further 10 min. The product which separated on pouring the reaction mixture in water was crystallised from xylene in light yellow beads (0.4 g.), m.p. 208°–9°. (Found : C, 72.36; H, 3.92. $C_{16}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 72.18; H, 3.79%).

The 2,4-D.N.P. : Prepared as usual and crystallised from nitrobenzene gave m.p. 330° (decomp.). (Found : N, 12.21. $C_{22}H_{14}O_7$ requires N, 12.55%).

3'-Formyl-4'-carbethoxymethoxyflavone : 3'-Formyl-4'-hydroxyflavone (1.5 g.) was refluxed with ethyl

bromoacetate (1 ml.) and anhydrous potassium carbonate (3 g.) in dry acetone for 10 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured in water and the ester obtained was crystallised from benzene. M.P. 184°. Yield 0.7 g. (Found : C, 68.42; H, 4.52. $C_{20}H_{16}O_6$ requires, C, 68.18; H, 4.58%).

3'-Formyl-4'-carboxymethoxyflavone : The preceding compound (1 g.) was kept with con. sulphuric acid at room temperature for 4 hr. It was then poured in water and crystallised from nitrobenzene. M.P. 270°. (Found : C, 66.62. H, 3.82. $C_{18}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 66.67; H, 3.73%).

2-(5'-Benzofuranyl) chromone : The above acid (1 g.) was refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (5 ml.) on a sand bath for 4 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured in water. The solid obtained was crystallised from dilute acetic acid. M.P. 165°. (Found : C, 77.75; H, 4.18. $C_{17}H_{10}O_3$ requires C, 77.86; H, 3.81%).

2-(6'-Coumarinyl) chromone : 3'-Formyl-4'-hydroxyflavone (1 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (5 ml.) and refluxed with freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) at 170°–80° in an oil bath for 12 hr. The reaction mixture was then poured in water. The product which separated crystallised from dilute acetic acid in light brown needles (0.4 g.), m.p. 267°. (Found : C, 74.49; H, 3.46. $C_{18}H_{10}O_4$ requires C, 74.48; H, 3.47%).

2'-Methyl-3'-acetyl-2,6'-bichromonyl : 3'-Acetyl-4'-hydroxyflavone (1 g.) was mixed with freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (10 ml.). The reaction mixture was heated at 170°–80° in an oil bath for 12 hr. The product separating after pouring the reaction mixture in water was washed with sodium hydroxide solution and crystallised from dilute acetic acid in beads (0.3 g.), m.p. 290°. (Found : C, 72.49; H, 3.75. $C_{21}H_{14}O_5$ requires C, 72.81; H, 4.03).

References

- * Part VII, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1967, **44**, 135.
1. L. S. HATTORI, *Acta. phytochim.*, 1925, **2**, 99; *Chem. Abs.*, 1926, **20**, 2162.
 2. S. GROSSMANN and ST. W. KOSTANECKI, *Ber.*, 1900, **33**, 2516.
 3. C. W. WILSON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, **61**, 2303.